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STROKE AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE: EPIDEMIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS, AND MANAGEMENT ACROSS KIDNEY DISEASE STAGES

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ANNOTATION

Numerous studies report linkage between chronic kidney disease (CKD) and cerebrovascular disease. This association has been particularly strong for cerebral small vessel disease. Significant findings have emerged from studies ranging from case reports, small case series, and larger cohort investigations. The latter show a relationship between declining renal function, microvascular disease, and cognitive impairment. One troubling aspect has been the relative paucity of mechanistic investigations addressing the CKD-cerebrovascular disease linkage. Nevertheless, mechanistic observations have begun to emerge, showing cerebral microhemorrhage development in animal models of CKD independent of hypertension, an important co-morbidity in clinical studies. Initial cell culture studies show endothelial monolayer disruption by CKD serum, suggesting blood-brain barrier injury.

Keywords: kidney; microvascular disease; microbleeds; animal models

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ИНСУЛЬТ И ХРОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ПОЧЕК: ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЯ, ПАТОГЕНЕЗ И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ НА РАЗНЫХ СТАДИЯХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ПОЧЕК

АННОТАЦИЯ

Многочисленные исследования сообщают о связи между хронической болезнью почек (ХБП) и цереброваскулярными заболеваниями. Эта связь особенно сильна при заболевании мелких сосудов головного мозга. Значительные результаты были получены в результате исследований, начиная от отчетов о случаях заболевания, небольших серий случаев и более крупных когортных исследований. Последние показывают связь между снижением функции почек, микрососудистыми заболеваниями и когнитивными нарушениями. Одним из тревожных аспектов является относительная нехватка механистических исследований, посвященных связи ХБП и цереброваскулярных заболеваний. Тем не менее, начали появляться механистические наблюдения, показывающие развитие церебральных микрокровоизлияний на животных моделях ХБП независимо от гипертонии, важного сопутствующего заболевания в клинических исследованиях. Первоначальные исследования клеточных культур показывают разрушение монослоя эндотелия под действием сыворотки ХБП, что указывает на повреждение гематоэнцефалического барьера.

Ключевые слова: почка; микрососудистые заболевания; микрокровоотечения; модели животных

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INSULT VA SURUNKALI BUYRAK KASALLIGI: EPIDEMIOLOGIYA, PATOGENEZ VA BUYRAK KASALLIGI BOSQICHLARIDA DAVOLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar surunkali buyrak kasalligi (CKD) va serebrovaskulyar kasalliklar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik haqida xabar beradi. Bu assotsiatsiya, ayniqsa, kichik miya tomirlari kasalliklari uchun kuchli bo'lgan. Muhim topilmalar ish hisobotlari, kichik holatlar seriyasi va kattaroq kohort tekshiruvlarigacha bo'lgan tadqiqotlar natijasida paydo bo'ldi. Ikkinchisi buyrak funksiyasining pasayishi, mikrovaskulyar kasalliklar va kognitiv buzilishlar o'rtasidagi munosabatni ko'rsatadi. Xavotirli jihatlardan biri bu CKD-miya qon tomir kasalliklari bilan bog'liqligini ko'rsatadigan mexanik tadqiqotlarning nisbatan kamligi edi. Shunga qaramay, mexanik kuzatuvlar paydo bo'la boshladi, bu klinik tadqiqotlarda muhim birgalikdagi kasallik bo'lgan gipertenziyadan mustaqil bo'lgan CKD ning hayvon modellarida miya mikroqon ketishining rivojlanishini

ko'rsatadi. Dastlabki hujayra madaniyati tadqiqotlari CKD sarumi tomonidan endotelial monoqatlamning buzilishini ko'rsatadi, bu qon-miya to'sig'ining shikastlanishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: buyrak; mikrotomir kasalliklari; mikroqon ketish; hayvonlar modellari.

The kidney and brain share similar microvasculature and vasoregulation, leading to shared susceptibility to microvascular dysfunction [14]. Both organs are perfused by “low resistance” vascular circuits, which permit continuous high-volume blood flow during systole and diastole. While small vessels in other organs are protected by upstream vasoconstriction, small arteries in the brain and kidney are constantly exposed to fluctuations in pressure, and flow due to low vascular resistance and upstream vasodilation [10, 14]. CKD is prevalent in nearly one-third of patients presenting with ICH, and it is associated with much worse mortality compared with those with normal renal function.[21] The high CKD prevalence rates in those with ICH may be attributable to their disproportionate burden of resistant hypertension, which affects one-third of patients with an eGFR of 300mg/g.[22] In addition, people with CKD (particularly black patients) appear to have a greater presence and number of CMB, further increasing their vulnerability.[23] Mineral and bone abnormalities may also play a role since higher serum phosphate levels in these patients have been associated with an increased ICH risk, whereas low levels have been associated with an increased risk of cerebral infarction in haemodialysis patients.[24] Compounding the problem, CKD was predictive of poorer outcomes in acute ICH in a secondary analysis of INTERACT-2, although intensive BP reduction appears to be equally effective in those with reduced eGFR compared with those with normal renal function.[25] Patients with more advanced kidney failure had the highest risk of death or major disability at 90 days (adjusted OR 1.82, 95%CI 1.28 to 2.61). The kidney-brain axis refers to a relationship that exists under both physiological and pathophysiological circumstances. This relationship has been described as the “neglected kidney-brain axis” (5) because the critical interplay between these two organs that can lead to important neurological disease pathophysiology has only recently been recognized. The kidney and brain share similar anatomical and physiological features that render them vulnerable to the impact of traditional cardiovascular risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes, and smoking [6]. Both organs share a low vascular resistance system, allowing continuous high-volume perfusion [7]. Autoregulation allows constant blood flow despite fluctuations in blood pressure, to maintain cerebral perfusion pressure in the brain and GFR in the kidney. The “strain vessel hypothesis” has been proposed as a possible mechanism for the relationship between renal and cerebrovascular diseases whereby juxtamedullary afferent arterioles in the kidney and cerebral perforating arteries are both exposed to high pressure and have to maintain large pressure gradients, rendering them uniquely susceptible to hypertensive injury [8]. This hypertensive vascular injury is then clinically manifest as proteinuria and progressive GFR decline in the kidney, and as symptomatic stroke, silent cerebral small vessel disease and cognitive decline in the brain. It has also been hypothesized that there may be inflammatory cross-talk between the two organs that may also contribute to the cerebrovascular and neuropsychiatric disease burden observed in patients with CKD [19]. This cross-talk between the kidney and brain may include enhanced cytokine/chemokine release and production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in AKI or CKD leading to neuroinflammation, cytokine interaction with pathogenic neurotrophic factors through a disrupted blood-brain barrier, and activation of the brain renin-angiotensin system (RAS) contributing to oxidative stress via angiotensin II. The cytokines/chemokine release in CKD activates immune cells, neurons, and glial cells in the brain creating a cascade with release of more inflammatory molecules, which locally interact

with neurotrophic factors and with ROS, thus contributing to neuropsychiatric disorders. In the last decade, the kidney-brain interaction has garnered great interest resulting in numerous epidemiologic and mechanistic investigations. The kidney and brain share anatomical and functional characteristics making them vulnerable to similar vascular risk factors. For example, these organs require continuous and stable high blood flow in a low vascular resistance system. They are both dependent on short, small perforating arterioles which autoregulate perfusion pressure. Both the renovascular and cerebrovascular beds are susceptible to traditional arteriosclerotic risk factors, such as aging, diabetes, hypertension, and smoking. Indeed, one could argue that declining kidney function and cognition in the elderly stem from common vascular pathogenesis. For example, hypertension is a major perpetrator of arteriosclerosis, while diabetes mellitus promotes both athero- and arteriolosclerosis. However, patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) have a greater risk for cerebrovascular disease [1, 2] which is not explained by traditional vascular risk factors alone. Leukoaraiosis is significantly associated with higher risk of stroke, dementia, and death [7]. In the most advanced form of CKD, i.e., endstage kidney disease, there is high prevalence of WMH as well as global reduction in gray matter [8, 9]. These pathologies provide a mechanistic basis for the large-scale meta-analyses that have confirmed CKD as a significant independent risk factor for stroke [10, 11]. There is also a strong relationship between CKD and cognitive decline, and many have suggested that subclinical SVD underlies this association. In fact, patients with CKD have a typical SVD neuropsychological profile, i.e., loss of executive function and decreased processing speed [12–14]. Here, we will review unique, nontraditional factors in the uremic milieu that promote vascular injury. Further, we discuss how these factors may drive common pathways of endothelial and vascular wall damage and result in SVD phenotypes. Many of these associations are currently correlative and will require confirmation in mechanistic bench and clinical studies. With greatly increased risk of stroke and poorer outcomes, in this vulnerable group of patients, it is important that preventive strategies be better applied to reduce stroke rates. Traditionally, patients with advanced renal impairment have been excluded from randomized controlled trials (RCT) involving the impact of healthcare intervention on the occurrence of stroke. It has been the norm to apply treatment algorithms from the general population and extrapolate them to patients with CKD. However, the presumption of efficacy in this group of patients with multiple co-morbidities can be misleading. Control of hypertension remains the cornerstone of primary as well as secondary stroke prevention in the general population as well as in patients with nondialysis CKD. In earlier stages of CKD such as CKD [29] was seen between attained blood pressure (BP) and stroke risk. However, earlier studies showed a J-shaped relationship in patients with CKD with systolic BP. The occurrence of stroke in CKD patients, especially the manifold increased risk in ESRD patients is an expression of increased and accelerated atherosclerosis in this group. However, in comparison to cardiac disease, this has been relatively understudied. It is therefore important to understand the risks as well as benefits of established therapy for stroke management and prevention and apply them judiciously in all stages of CKD. The need of the hour are well-designed randomized controlled trials in CKD/ESRD and postrenal transplant patients that can address and provide answers to important questions in this vulnerable group.

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